

Review

Marchantia polymorpha as a Source of Biologically Active Compounds

Filip Nowaczyński ^{1,*}

¹ Department of Pharmacognosy with the Medicinal Plant Garden, Medical University of Lublin, 20-093 Lublin, Poland; agnieszka.ludwiczuk@umlub.pl

² Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Research Center for Olive, Fruit and Citrus Crops, 81100 Caserta, Italy

³ Department of Plant Protection, University of Life Sciences, 20-069 Lublin, Poland; beata.zimowska@up.lublin.pl

* Correspondence: filip.nowaczynski@umlub.pl (F.N.); rosario.nicoletti@crea.gov.it (R.N.)

Abstract: *Marchantia polymorpha* L., also known as common liverwort or umbrella liverwort, is a spore-forming plant belonging to the Marchantiaceae family. This thallose liverwort has gained importance as a model plant, mainly because of its global distribution and easy and rapid in vitro culturing. A review of the literature shows that the major compounds in this species are undoubtedly sesquiterpenoids and bisbibenzyls. Among the sesquiterpenoids, it is worth mentioning cuparenes, chamigranes, and thujopsanes. Compounds belonging to these classes were found in specimens from Japan, China, Poland, Germany, and India and could be the chemical markers of this liverwort species. The key secondary metabolite of *M. polymorpha* is a macrocyclic bisbibenzyl, marchantin A. Marchantin-type aromatic compounds, together with other bisbibenzyls, such as riccardin D, isoriccardin C, or perrottetin E, demonstrated antifungal and antibacterial properties in various studies. In this review, we summarize the current knowledge on the diversity of compounds produced by *M. polymorpha*, emphasizing chemical variability depending on the origin of the plant material. Moreover, the biological activity of extracts obtained from this liverwort species, as well as single secondary metabolites, are described.

Academic Editors: Vlasios Goulas and Andreas Tzakos

Received: 24 December 2024

Revised: 20 January 2025

Accepted: 24 January 2025

Published: 26 January 2025

Citation: Nowaczyński, F.; Nicoletti, R.; Zimowska, B.; Ludwiczuk, A. *Marchantia polymorpha* as a Source of Biologically Active Compounds. *Molecules* **2025**, *30*, 558. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules30030558>

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Keywords: common liverwort; terpenoids; bisbibenzyls; biological activity; Marchantiaceae

1. Introduction

Bryophytes are terrestrial, spore-bearing plants that comprise three phyla: liverworts (Marchantiophyta), mosses (Bryophyta), and hornworts (Anthoceroophyta). These small nonvascular plants, phylogenetically placed between algae and ferns, are considered the first inhabitants of terrestrial habitats [1]. As the first land plants, they had to cope with adverse environmental conditions; hence, their ability to synthesize many different specialized secondary metabolites is extremely high. Indeed, such ‘chemical weapons’ are necessary for these small plants, since they lack mechanical protection of higher vascular plants [2]. Among the bryophytes, the chemical constituents of the Marchantiophyta and their biological activity have been studied in great detail. Over the last 40 years, more than 3000 compounds have been found in this group of plants. Many of these products are characterized by unprecedented structures, and some, including the pinguisane-type sesquiterpenoids and the sacculatane-type diterpenoids, have not been found in any other plants, fungi, or marine organisms. This unique chemical composition increases the number of potential applications in medicine and beyond. In fact, the available literature data

indicate that liverwort secondary metabolites show antibacterial, antifungal, cytotoxic, insect repellent, enzyme inhibitory, and proapoptotic activities [3–5].

Marchantia polymorpha L., also known as common liverwort or umbrella liverwort and belonging to the Marchantiaceae family (Figure 1), is the most widely distributed liverwort in the world. It is a cosmopolitan species that occurs from tropical to arctic regions [6,7].

Figure 1. *Marchantia polymorpha*—umbrella liverwort: (a) female and (b) male plant. (Photos by Prof. Yoshinori Asakawa, Tokushima Bunri University, Japan).

This liverwort species has become one of the most important models for plant biology research and evolutionary genomics due to its relatively simple genome, global distribution, easy *in vitro* culturing, and unique phylogenetic position as a member of the early land plants [8,9]. As an evolutionary model, *M. polymorpha* contributes to our understanding of the evolution of plant defensive responses and the associated hormonal signaling pathways [9]. At this point, the following questions arise about the biologically active compounds present in this model plant: What do we know about them? Does *Marchantia* have its own characteristic metabolites? And are they used in medicine, horticulture, or for other purposes?

The aim of this paper is to review the available scientific literature concerning both the chemical composition and the biological properties of the most well-known liverwort species, *M. polymorpha*. Special attention was paid to the variability of the chemical composition depending on the origin of the plant material.

2. Chemical Diversity of *M. polymorpha*

Liverworts (Marchantiophyta) are plants that produce a wide array of biologically active secondary metabolites. These compounds are accumulated in the oil bodies, which are prominent and highly distinctive organelles uniquely found in liverworts [10]. Oil bodies are present in 95% of all liverwort species and are intracellular organelles bounded by a single unit membrane originating from dilated endoplasmic reticulum cisternae, containing lipophilic globules [11]. In the thallose liverworts like *M. polymorpha*, oil bodies are confined to scattered idioblastic oil body cells, while oil bodies of leafy liverworts are generally present in all cells [12]. The number, size, and colour of oil bodies are species specific. Oil bodies are estimated to serve a protective role for the plant, with their contents postulated to protect the plant against various biotic and abiotic stressors [13].

A review of the literature on the chemical composition of the umbrella liverwort shows that it is characterized by great diversity. The following groups of chemical compounds have been identified so far in *Marchantia*: monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and diterpenoids; sterols and triterpenoids; and bibenzyls, bisbibenzyls, phenanthrene derivatives, flavonoids, lipids, and other compounds (Table 1).

Table 1. Secondary metabolites found in *Marchantia polymorpha*.

No.	Compounds	Formula	Geographic Origin	References
<i>MONOTERPENOIDS</i>				
1	Limonene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	USA *	[14]
<i>SESQUITERPENOIDS</i>				
acoranens				
2	β-Acoradiene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Poland	[15]
3	α-Neocallitropsene	C ₁₅ H ₂₆	Poland	[15]
4	β-Alaskene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Poland	[15]
5	Acorenone B	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	Poland	[15]
aromadendranes				
6	α-Gurjunene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Serbia, Turkey, USA *	[14,16,17]
7	Aromadendrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Turkey	[16]
8	Viridiflorol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Serbia	[17]
barbatenes				
9	α-Barbatene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan	[18]
10	β-Barbatene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan, Turkey	[16,18–20]
bisabolanes				
11	β-Bisabolene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan	[19]
caryophyllanes				
12	β-Caryophyllene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan	[19]
cedranes				
13	α-Cedrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan	[19]
14	7-epi-α-Cedrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Poland	[15]
15	β-Cedrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	France	[21]
chamigranes				
16	α-Chamigrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan, Germany, India	[20,22,23]
17	β-Chamigrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Germany, India, Poland, Japan, France, Serbia, USA *	[14,15,17,19,22–25]
18	<i>ent</i> -9-oxo-α-Chamigrene (Laurenconone C)	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O	Japan, Germany, Poland	[20,22,24]
cuparanes				
19	Cuparene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan, Poland, France, Serbia, USA *	[14,15,17–19,25]
20	α-Cuprenene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan, France, Poland	[15,19,20]
21	β-Cuprenene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan, France	[19]
22	γ-Cuprenene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan	[20]
23	δ-Cuprenene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan, France, Poland	[15,19,20]
24	β-Microbiotene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Poland	[15]
25	2-Cuparenol (=Cuparophenol, δ-Cuparenol, 2-Hydroxycuparene)	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O	South Africa, Japan, France	[18,19,24,26]
26	<i>ent</i> -Cuprenenol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Japan, France	[19]

Table 1. Cont.

No.	Compounds	Formula	Geographic Origin	References
27	Cyclopropanecuparenol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Japan, France, Poland, Serbia	[15,17,19,20]
28	<i>epi</i> -Cyclopropanecuparenol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Japan, France, Poland	[15,19]
cyclomylytaylanes				
29	Cyclomylytaylenol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Serbia	[17]
elemenes and bicycloelemenes				
30	β-Elemene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan	[19,21]
31	δ-Elemene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan	[19,24,25]
32	Bicycloelemene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan, France	[19]
eudesmanes				
33	α-Selinene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Turkey, Poland, Serbia	[15,17,19]
34	<i>ent</i> -β-Selinene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	India, Japan	[19,23]
35	α-Eudesmol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Turkey	[16]
36	β-Eudesmol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Turkey	[16]
eremophilanes				
37	Eremophilene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	France	[21]
38	1(10),11-Eremophiladien-9β-ol	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	Germany	[27]
germacranes				
39	Costunolide	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₂	Japan	[28]
guaianes				
40	5-Guaia-11-ol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Serbia	[17]
herbertanes				
41	β-Herbertenol	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O	Japan, Poland	[15,18,19]
42	<i>ent</i> -α-Herbertenol	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O	Germany	[22]
himachalanes				
43	α-Himachalene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	USA *	[14,25]
monocyclofarnesanes				
44	(2 <i>Z</i> ,4 <i>E</i>)-Abscisic acid	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₃	USA	[29]
45	(2 <i>E</i> ,4 <i>E</i>)-Abscisic acid	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₃	USA	[29]
thujopsanes				
46	<i>ent</i> -Thujopsene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	Japan, Poland, France, Serbia, USA *	[14,15,17–20,30]
47	<i>ent</i> -Thujopsan-7β-ol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Japan, Germany	[20,22]
48	<i>ent</i> -Thujopsenone (=Thujops-3-en-5-one)	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O	Japan, France, Serbia	[17–20]
widdranes				
49	Widdrol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	Japan	[18,19]
DITERPENOIDS				
50	Marchanol	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₂	Vietnam	[31]
51	Labda-7,13 <i>E</i> -dien-15-ol	C ₂₀ H ₃₄ O	Japan	[19,30,32]

Table 1. Cont.

No.	Compounds	Formula	Geographic Origin	References
52	Vitexilactone	C ₂₂ H ₃₄ O ₄	Vietnam	[31]
53	Phytol	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	South Africa, Poland	[15,19,33]
<i>STEROLS and TRITERPENOIDS</i>				
54	Campesterol	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ O	South Africa, Germany, Japan, India, Taiwan	[22–24,33,34]
55	Brassicasterol	C ₂₈ H ₄₆ O	Japan	[24]
56	Dihydrobrassicasterol	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ O	Taiwan	[34]
57	Stigmasterol	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O	South Africa, Japan, Germany	[22,24,33]
58	Sitosterol	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O	South Africa, Germany, Taiwan	[22,33,34]
59	Clionasterol (24β-ethyl)	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O	Taiwan	[34]
60	12-Oleanene-3-one	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O	Vietnam	[31]
61	Ursolic acid	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₃	Vietnam	[31]
62	3,11-Dioxoursolic acid	C ₃₀ H ₄₄ O ₄	Vietnam	[31]
<i>BIBENZYL</i>				
63	Lunularin	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₂	Germany, Vietnam, China)	[19,22,31,35]
64	Lunularic acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄	Japan *, Germany	[36–38]
65	Prelunularic acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₅	Japan	[38,39]
66	2,5-Di-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-4'-hydroxybibenzyl	C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₁₃	China	[40]
67	2-[3-(Hydroxymethyl)phenoxy]-3-[2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)ethyl]phenol	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₄	China	[41]
<i>BISBIBENZYL</i>				
68	Riccardin C (=plagiochin G)	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	South Africa, India, Vietnam, China	[23,31,33,35]
69	Riccardin D (=plagiochin E)	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	China	[42]
70	Riccardin G (=plagiochin E methyl ether)	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₄	China *	[35]
71	Riccardin H	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ O ₄	China	[42]
72	Isoriccardin C	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	India, Vietnam	[23,31]
73	Isoriccardin D	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	China	[41]
74	13,13'-O-Isopropylidenericcardin D	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ O ₄	China	[42]
75	Polymorphatin A	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	China	[41]
76	Marchantin A	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₅	China, Germany, India, Japan, Serbia, Vietnam	[19,22,23,25,30,31,35,42–46]
77	7',8'-Dehydromarchantin A	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	Serbia *	[43]
78	Marchantin B	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₆	China, Germany Japan	[19,22,30,35,42,43,45]
79	Marchantin C	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	South Africa, Germany, India, Japan, Serbia *	[19,22,23,30,33,43,45]
80	Marchantin D	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₆	Germany, India, China	[22,23,30,35,45,47]

Table 1. Cont.

No.	Compounds	Formula	Geographic Origin	References
81	Marchantin E	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₆	China, Germany, India, France, Serbia *	[19,22,23,30,35,42,43,45]
82	Marchantin F	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₇	South Africa, China	[35]
83	Marchantin G	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₆	Japan	[47]
84	Marchantin H	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₅	South Africa,	[33]
85	Marchantin J	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ O ₆	China, Germany	[22,41]
86	Marchantin K	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₇	Germany, Vietnam, China	[22,31,35]
87	Marchantin L	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₆	Germany	[22]
88	Isomarchantin C	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	India	[23]
89	Neomarchantin A	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	China	[42]
90	Perrottetin E	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₄	China, India	[23,35,41]
<i>OTHER AROMATICS</i>				
91	3R-(3,4-Dimethoxybenzyl)-5,7-dimethoxyphthalide	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₆	Vietnam	[31]
92	Marchatoside	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₇	Vietnam	[31]
93	3-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-8-hydroxyisocoumarin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	Germany *	[37]
94	2,3-Dimethoxy-7-hydroxy-phenanthrene	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃	Germany *	[37]
95	2,7-Dihydroxy-3-methoxy-phenanthrene	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃	Germany *	[37]
96	3,3'-Dimethoxy-2,2',7,7'-tetrahydroxy-1,1'-biphenanthrene	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ O ₆	Germany *	[37]
97	2-Hydroxy-3,7-dimethoxy phenanthrene	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃	India	[23]
98	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	C ₇ H ₆ O ₂	Germany	[22]
99	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	C ₇ H ₆ O ₂	South Africa, Germany	[22,33]
100	3-Methoxy-2,2',3',7,7'-pentahydroxy-1,1'-biphenanthrene	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ O ₆	Germany *	[37]
101	2,2',3,3',7,7'-Hexahydroxy-1,1'-biphenanthrene	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ O ₆	Germany *	[37]
102	2-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-ethyl-β-D-allopyranoside	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₈	China	[40]
103	2-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-ethyl-β-D-glucopyranoside	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₈	China, Germany *, Japan	[37,40,48]
104	2-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-ethyl-O-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)-β-D-allopyranoside	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ O ₁₂	China	[40]
105	2-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-ethyl-O-β-D-xylopyranosyl-(1→6)-O-β-D-allopyranoside	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₁₂	China	[40]
106	Salidroside	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₇	Japan	[48]
107	Indole acetic acid	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ N	USA	[29]

Table 1. Cont.

No.	Compounds	Formula	Geographic Origin	References
<i>FLAVONOIDS</i>				
108	Apigenin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	Germany *, New Zealand	[37,49,50]
109	Apigenin-7-O-β-D-glucuronide	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₁	New Zealand	[49,50]
110	Apigenin-7,4'-di-O-glucuronide	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₁₇	New Zealand	[49,50]
111	Luteolin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	Germany	[22,49,50]
112	Luteolin-7-O-β-D-glucuronide	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₂	New Zealand	[49,50]
113	Luteolin-7,3'-di-O-β-glucuronide	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₁₈	New Zealand	[49,50]
114	Luteolin-7,4'-di-O-β-glucuronide	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₁₈	New Zealand	[49,50]
115	Luteolin-3',4'-di-O-β-glucuronide	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₁₈	New Zealand	[49,50]
116	Luteolin-3'-O-β-glucuronide	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₂	New Zealand	[49,50]
117	Luteolin-7,3',4'-tri-O-β-glucuronide		New Zealand	[49,50]
118	Artemetin	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₈	Vietnam	[31]
119	Kaempferol	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	Vietnam	[31]
120	Quercetin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	Vietnam	[31]
121	Aureusidin-6-O-glucuronide	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₂	New Zealand	[51]
122	5,3',4'-Trihydroxyisoflavone-7-O-β-D-glucopyranoside (=Orobol-7-O-glucoside)	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	China	[40]
123	Riccionidin A	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₆	Germany *	[52]
124	Riccionidin B	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ O ₁₂	Germany *	[52]
<i>LIPIDS</i>				
125	Palmitic acid (16:0) (=Hexadecanoic acid)	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	Japan *	[20,53]
126	Ethyl palmitate (=Hexadecanoic acid ethyl ester)	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	Japan	[20]
127	Stearic acid (18:0) (=Octadecanoic acid)	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	Japan *	[53]
128	Palmitoleic acid (16:1n-7) (=9-Hexadecenoic acid)	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₂	Japan *	[53]
129	Oleic acid (18:1n-9) (=9-Octadecenoic acid)	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	Japan *	[53]
130	Linoleic acid (18:2n-6) (=9,12-Octadecadienoic acid)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	Japan *	[20,53]
131	α-Linolenic acid (18:3n-3) (=9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid)	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂	Japan *	[53]
132	Arachidonic acid (20:4n-6) (=5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid)	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₂	Japan *	[53,54]
133	EPA (20:5n-3) (=5,8,11,14,17-Eicosapentaenoic acid)	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ O ₂	Japan *	[53,54]
134	Oxacycloheptadecan-2-one	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₂	Japan	[20]
<i>OTHER COMPOUNDS</i>				
135	Shikimic acid 4-(β-D-xylopyranoside)	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O ₉	China	[40]

* axenic or cell culture.

Table 2. Cont.

Characteristic Compounds	Subspecies				Geographical Origin										
	Mpr	Mpp	Mpm	Japan	Poland	Germany	France	Serbia	Turkey	India	China	Vietnam	South Africa	USA	
BISBIBENZYL															
Marchantin A	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓			
Marchantin B				✓		✓					✓				
Marchantin C	✓			✓		✓		✓*		✓				✓	
Marchantin D						✓				✓	✓				
Marchantin E	✓					✓	✓	✓*		✓	✓				
Marchantin F											✓			✓	
Marchantin G				✓											
Marchantin H														✓	
Marchantin J						✓					✓				
Marchantin K						✓					✓	✓			
Marchantin L						✓									
Isomarchantin C										✓					
Neomarchantin A											✓				
Riccardin C										✓	✓	✓	✓		
Riccardin D											✓				
Riccardin G											✓*				
Riccardin H											✓				
Isoriccardin C										✓		✓			
Isoriccardin D											✓				
Perrottetin E										✓	✓				

* cell culture; Mpr—*M. polymorpha* subsp. *ruderalis*; Mpp—*M. polymorpha* subsp. *polymorpha*; Mpm—*M. polymorpha* subsp. *montivagans*.

2.1. Sesquiterpenoids

Marchantia polymorpha is a rich source of terpenoids, in particular those belonging to the sesquiterpene group. Forty-eight sesquiterpenoids belonging to twenty different classes are included in Table 1. The structures of selected sesquiterpenoids characteristic of *M. polymorpha* are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Selected sesquiterpenoids characteristic of *M. polymorpha*.

The first sesquiterpenoid reported from *M. polymorpha* was (*S*)-2-hydroxycuparene (=2-cuparenol). Its isolation was conducted in 1974 by Hopkins and Perold [26] from a South African specimen. Two cuparane-type alcohols, cyclopropanecuparenol and its epimer, are the major volatile components of this species. Besides the mentioned alcohols, other cuparanes are present in *M. polymorpha*, namely cuparene and α-, β-, γ-, and δ-cuprenene.

Thujopsanes and chamigranes are other sesquiterpenoids characteristic of *M. polymorpha*. They are represented by thujopsene, thujopsan-7 β -ol, thujopsenone, α - and β -chamigrene, as well as *ent*-9-oxo- α -chamigrene [12,18]. The data included in Table 2 show that these sesquiterpenoids (cuparanes, chamigranes, and thujopsanes) could be chemical markers of *M. polymorpha* subsp. *ruderalis*. Occasionally, this subspecies can produce metabolites characteristic of a single specimen. In the Polish collection of *M. polymorpha*, acorane-type sesquiterpenoids were identified. The presence of α -neocallitropsene, acorenone B, β -alaskene, and β -acoradiene were confirmed [59,60].

Our recent preliminary data concerning volatile components present in the Serbian *M. polymorpha* subspecies showed that the subspecies *polymorpha* and *montivagans* are very different with reference to sesquiterpene composition. In the case of these subspecies, the presence of cuparane-, chamigrane-, and thujopsane-type compounds was not demonstrated, while compounds belonging to aromadendranes, guaianes, and eudesmanes were identified [17]. A very similar chemical composition was also observed in the sample from Turkey [16]. Although the authors did not specify the subspecies of the specimen studied, it can be inferred that it is not *M. ruderalis*.

2.2. Bibenzyls and Bisbibenzyls

Bibenzyls are organic compounds with a C₆-C₂-C₆ skeleton, which are synthesized by the phenylpropanoid pathway, like polyphenols [61]. Common liverwort is reported to produce only a few compounds; among them, it is worth mentioning lunularin and lunularic acid [23,26,62]. Both metabolites are direct precursors in the biosynthesis of marchantin C, a bisbibenzyl, which is later transformed to form marchantin A [63].

Bisbibenzyls are macrocyclic compounds consisting of two bibenzyl units. Acyclic bisbibenzyl compounds are linked once, while the cyclic ones are linked twice. The most important bisbibenzyl found in *M. polymorpha* is marchantin A. It is derived from lunularic acid, with two ether linkages between C₁-C_{2'} and between C₁₄-C_{11'} (Figure 3). The majority of common liverwort specimens contain marchantin A in large amounts. In fact, it was reported to be present in common liverwort from various countries (Table 1). This, however, is not true for South African *M. polymorpha*, which, according to some studies, does not contain marchantin A at all [33]. Its place as the major cyclic bisbibenzyl is taken by marchantin H. Moreover, marchantin E has been isolated from Indian and French specimens [5]. Marchantin A is also commonly found in many other plants from the Marchantiales [64,65] and other Marchantiophyta [66].

Riccardins are another group of cyclic bisbibenzyl compounds present in *M. polymorpha*. Japanese and Indian specimens of *M. polymorpha* contain riccardin C [13,22,40]. Riccardin H, isoriccardin D, and 13,13'-*O*-isopropylidenericcardin D were found in *M. polymorpha* from China [62]. Isoriccardin C was found in Chinese, Indian, and Vietnamese plant material [13,62,67].

Other bisbibenzyls that can be found in common liverwort are perrottetin E and polymorphatin A. Perrottetin E is an acyclic bisbibenzyl found in Indian and Chinese specimens of common liverwort [13,62]. It can be used as a precursor for the synthesis of marchantin- and riccardin-type compounds [33]. Polymorphatin A is a cyclic compound linked with one ether C₁-C_{2'} linkage and one biphenyl C₁₂-C_{12'} linkage. This bisbibenzyl was first found in Chinese *M. polymorpha* [62]. Representatives of riccardins and other bisbibenzyls are presented in Figure 4.

Based on the data presented in Table 2, specimens from European countries and Japan are characterized by the occurrence of only marchantin A derivatives. On the other hand, those from India, China, and Vietnam, as well as South Africa, in addition to marchantin-type compounds, also produce those belonging to the riccardin and perrottetin types.

Figure 3. Chemical structures of marchantin-type bisbibenzyls.

Figure 4. Chemical structures of some riccardins and perrottetin E.

2.3. Other Compounds

Flavonoids are ubiquitous minor components in the Marchantiophyta, including *M. polymorpha* [3,4,68]. The main flavonoid types present in this species are flavone O-glucuronides. Luteolin, apigenin, and their derivatives are the most abundant, as shown in Table 1.

Another interesting biochemical feature of *M. polymorpha* is represented by two polyunsaturated fatty acids, arachidonic acid (ARA, 20:4n-6) and eicosapentenoic acid (EPA, 20:5n-3). Shinmen et al. [54] have reported that culture of *M. polymorpha* contained high amounts of ARA and EPA (92 and 48 mg L⁻¹, respectively) under photomixotrophic conditions.

Among other products of *M. polymorpha*, it is worth mentioning monoterpenoids and diterpenoids, sterols and triterpenoids, phenanthrenes, phthalides, and other aromatic compounds. Characteristic diterpenoids can be found in Vietnamese specimens, such as marchanol, belonging to the clerodane-type compounds, and vitexilactone from the labdane group [31].

Marchantia polymorpha does not synthesize monoterpenes, apart from limonene, which was reported at the initial stage of growth in cell culture [14].

The sterols and triterpenoids found in common liverwort are similar to those found in the higher plants. Among the sterols, the presence of sitosterol and stigmasterol was confirmed, while among triterpenoids, the occurrence of ursane- and oleanane-type compounds was reported [22,31,33]. Phenanthrene derivatives were found in the field collection of *M. polymorpha* from India [23], as well as from cell cultures in Germany [37]. Finally, the presence of two phthalides, 3R-(3,4-dimethoxybenzyl)-5,7-dimethoxyphthalide and marchatoside, was confirmed in a Vietnamese collection [31].

The chemical structures of selected diterpenoids and triterpenoids, flavonoids, phenanthrenes, and phthalides are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Chemical structures of some diterpenoids and triterpenoids, flavonoids, phenanthrenes, and phthalides.

3. Biological Activities

Common liverwort has a long history in ethnomedicine [64]. It was used as an antipyretic, antihepatic, antidotal, and a diuretic medicinal plant [69].

Extracts of *M. polymorpha* were repeatedly proven to possess antifungal properties [42,70–73]. Many fungi are susceptible to growth inhibition when subjected to these extracts, including *Candida albicans* [35,70,74], *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Tilletia indica*, *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *lini*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Rhizoctonia solani* [42,71], *Alternaria solani* [74], *Fusarium solani* [73], and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* [35,74]. Studies of activity against *C. albicans* determined that neomarchantin A, riccardin D, and 13,13'-O-isopropylidene-riccardin D are the most effective compounds, while marchantin A, B, and E and riccardin H, even if possessing some antifungal activity, were not as effective [70]. The activity also varies depending on the solvent used for extraction. Riccardin D (called by the authors plagiochin E), found in Chinese *M. polymorpha*, exhibits inhibitory properties against *C. albicans*, which were increased when combined with fluconazole. When examined in more detail, this compound was found to reverse the fungal resistance to the azole drug by inhibiting its efflux from *C. albicans* [75]. Transmission electron microscopy showed serious damage in the structure of the yeast cell wall after treatment with plagiochin E. Inhibition of chitin synthesis was detected, deriving from downregulation of the expression of *CHS1* and upregulation of the expression of *CHS2* and *CHS3* [76]. Moreover, exposure to plagiochin E resulted in an elevation of the membrane potential and a decrease of the ATP level in mitochondria, which caused ROS accumulation [77]. This effect induced typical markers of apoptosis in the yeast cells, such as chromatin condensation, nuclear fragmentation, and G₂/M cell cycle arrest. The latter event was related to downregulation of cyclins (CDC28, CLB2 and CLB4), as well as metacaspase activation [78].

Antibacterial activity of extracts from *M. polymorpha* is also an important subject of studies on common liverwort, although no information has been collected so far with reference to the mechanisms of action. Besides the crude extracts [71,74], marchantin A also exhibits such properties; in fact, its inhibitory effect has been documented on both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, such as *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Neisseria meningitidis*, *Pasteurella multocida*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, and *Streptococcus viridans* [23,42,62,68,79,80]. Antibacterial effects have been also documented in the case of isoriccardin C [62]. Lines of *M. polymorpha* were also subjected to genetic engineering in order to obtain a mutant with a higher potential for the synthesis of antibacterial compounds [35].

In vitro studies have shown that organic extracts of *M. polymorpha* exhibit cytotoxic activity [81,82], deriving from their content in bioactive products. A more detailed study conducted in 2008 showed that marchantin A induces growth inhibition on the breast cancer cell lines A256, MCF-7, and T47D, based on an antimicrotubular effect which was increased when marchantin A and an Aurora-A kinase inhibitor were used simultaneously [83]. Marchantin A also demonstrated cytotoxicity against the malignant melanoma cell line A375 while having less cytotoxic activity against keratocytes and not affecting tyrosinase activity in a model assay [84]. Lunularin also exhibited potent cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 [62].

Marchantin A exhibits DNA polymerase β -inhibitory and anti-HIV activities [85]. Moreover, along with marchantins B and E, plagiochin A, and perrottetin F, it possesses anti-influenza activity deriving from its targeting of the PA subunit of endonuclease. These products have a 3,4-dihydroxyphenethyl group in common, which is indicative of the importance of this moiety for this kind of bioactivity [86]. Marchantin A was also found to inhibit the proliferation of the erythrocytic stages of two *Plasmodium falciparum* strains, as well as other protozoans, such as *Trypanosoma brucei rhodesiense*, *T. cruzi*, and *Leishmania donovani* [87]. Its antitrypanosomal activity was also documented by another research

group, along with marchantin E [88]. However, marchantin A has a low sensitivity index towards the aforementioned parasites, so the therapeutic window is rather narrow [1].

While tested for its antioxidant properties, marchantin A showed free radical scavenging ability [35] depending on its concentration. It also ties in to the anti-inflammatory properties of *M. polymorpha*, originating in its ethnomedicinal uses. Marchantins A, B, D, and E, isoriccardin C, and perrotetin D demonstrated an inhibitory effect on 5-lipoxygenase and cyclooxygenase, key enzymes in the arachidonic acid cascade [89]. The strength of this effect is structure dependent, as marchantin D exhibited lower inhibition toward 5-lipoxygenase. Along with lunularin, isoriccardin C has also displayed strong DPPH radical scavenging activity [62].

A chloroform extract of *M. polymorpha* was postulated to have hepatoprotective properties [90]. When mice were administered with paracetamol in liver-damaging quantities along with marchantin A, the amount of markers of liver damage in mice blood (aspartate transaminase and alanine transaminase) was significantly lower than in the control group administered with paracetamol only, and on par with the group in which paracetamol was administered along with silymarin. Another study showed that flavonoids of *M. polymorpha* can protect liver cells from injuries caused by the administration of carbon tetrachloride [91]. As both compounds induce damage to liver cells with their oxidizing potential, the hepatoprotective effect was postulated to be due to the antioxidant properties of *M. polymorpha* extracts.

Marchantin A, riccardin A, marchantin B, and other compounds from *M. polymorpha* also have an inhibitory effect on lipopolysaccharide production induced by nitric oxide [92]. As nitric oxide is postulated to play a role in the etiology of chronic neurodegenerative diseases [93], this property should be more closely investigated in the future.

Structural similarity between cyclic bisbenzyl compounds and bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids, such as tubocurarine, has led to the investigation of the muscle relaxation properties of marchantin-type compounds [94]. In a study published in 1995 [95], marchantin A was used in comparison to cepharanthine, a muscle relaxant. Both compounds expressed similar properties and were bound to a common receptor, which points to the muscle-relaxing properties of marchantin A likely being owed to the binding of calcium molecules. This may also tie in with the inhibition by marchantin A of calmodulin [95], a protein with activity related to calcium levels in the cell.

4. Conclusions and Future Perspectives

Although bryophytes are among the oldest land plants, their usefulness is relatively unknown to most people. There is very little knowledge available about the medicinal properties of bryophytes. An ancient method of determining the medicinal properties of plants was based on the concept of Paracelsus, dealing with the resemblance of plant body parts to the shape and structure of organs in the human or animal body for which it is remedial. As per the abovementioned philosophy, *M. polymorpha* was used to cure hepatic disorders [96]. This liverwort was also used as a medicine for boils and abscesses, perhaps because the young archegoniophore resembles a boil when it first emerges from the thallus [97].

From this perspective *M. polymorpha* became a very interesting case study. This liverwort is present in almost all environments and has a very versatile phytochemical profile, especially including bisbenzyl compounds. These compounds are almost unique to liverworts, as their presence has so far only been confirmed for plants of the *Primula* genus [1,5]; they have disclosed particular interest in biological activity studies and may be the foundation of new plant medicines or plant protection products.

However, until now, no products derived from *M. polymorpha* are available on the market. Also, to the best of our knowledge, no clinical, pre-clinical or toxicological studies have been carried out so far. Although the exact mode of action of some of the described bioactive compounds remains unknown, *M. polymorpha* and its metabolites could serve as an attractive candidate for therapeutic properties. Further work on the isolation, characterization, structural elucidation, pharmacological evaluation, determination of mode of action, and clinical trial of these active principles could open exciting perspectives in future drug development programs.

The secondary metabolites of *M. polymorpha* endophytes show applicative potential as well. They exhibit selective cytotoxicity toward several cancer cell lines and antiviral properties [15,98], calling for more accurate investigations on their occurrence and bioactivities. As of late, our team is trying to establish the optimal ways to cultivate these bryophytes and to extract and evaluate their products.

As we managed to summarize in this article, the therapeutic potential of *M. polymorpha* is yet to be fully explored, but, even now, it holds potential for many future studies, which may result in crucial findings.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, A.L., F.N. and B.Z.; methodology, A.L.; formal analysis, R.N.; investigation, F.N.; resources, A.L.; data curation, B.Z. and A.L.; writing—original draft preparation, F.N, B.Z. and A.L.; writing—review and editing, R.N.; visualization, A.L. and F.N.; supervision, R.N.; project administration, A.L.; funding acquisition, R.N. and A.L. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was funded by project 101135305—HORIZON-CL6-2023-CircBio-01-4 (Bio-prospecting and production of bioactive molecules from European bryophytes ‘BRYOMOLECULES’).

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: No new data were created.

Acknowledgments: The authors gratefully acknowledge the contribution of Yoshinori Asakawa (Tokushima Bunri University, Japan) for the valuable scientific discussion and photos of umbrella liverwort.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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